

Reforming Research Assessment at Mid Sweden University - CoARA Action Plan 2023–2028

Background

Mid Sweden University, Miun, is a global university with a regional commitment where we do research and educate for life. Our work leads to increased attractiveness, relevance, and quality, as well as a sustainable development.

Globally, there is a consensus that reforms to research assessment are needed to enhance quality and foster strong research cultures. CoARA, Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, is a recent global initiative dedicated to advancing changes in research evaluation to recognize diverse outputs, practices, and activities maximizing impact. Founded on ten commitments, the coalition provides a unified framework for assessing research, researchers, and institutions. It involves qualitative evaluations emphasizing peer-review, complemented by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

By joining the coalition in October 2023, Miun committed to reforming its research assessment practices in line with CoARA guidelines. Research organizations are at the same time encouraged to design context-specific assessments that safekeep their autonomy, and tailor research evaluations that monitor specific institutional values. Members are urged to share their progress within a year, following an Action Plan with a 5-year time frame. Miun's plan presents prioritized areas and broadly outlined reforms, detailing contributions from researchers and other personnel, as well as ongoing collaborative efforts. Progress will be monitored through annual updates emphasizing advancements.

Prioritized areas

Miun's vision, strategy, and organizational characteristics have guided collaborative reflections on the CoARA core commitments, identifying priority areas for reform. Our efforts will focus on the following areas:

Miun is active in the work of open science as a vital foundation for ensuring the integrity, quality, and relevance of research

Miun advocates the recognition and inclusion of diverse research merits in the planning and assessment of research careers, such as valuing collaboration with the surrounding community in research.

Miun upholds stringent standards for research quality and integrity by continually enhancing the methods of collegial research evaluation

Action plan and timeframe

CoARA requires simultaneous reforms and changes in attitude within the research community. *What do we need to change, how and when?*

Goals	Actions	Responsibility
A. Miun encourages cultural changes within the organization by further enhancing attitudes, work procedures, and practices related to science, recruitment, and research evaluation.	<p>2025</p> <p>Establish and implement a communication plan to ensure that all relevant staff and researchers are up to date regarding Miun's strategy and CoARA priorities. Make sure that communication efforts are continuous and interactive and include for example workshops, forums for discussion, and platforms</p> <p>2026 – 2028</p> <p>Encourage changes in mindset and methods through communication, dialogue, guidelines and training. Examples of measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - revise assessment criteria, processes, and tools - revise administrative tools and templates for recruitment and career development 	Head of the communications department together with Deputy vice-chancellor for quality, University director, Deans

	based on new recommendations	
B. Miun is active in the work with open science as a vital foundation for ensuring the integrity, quality, and relevance of research.	<p>2025</p> <p>Implement Open access and data etc (look at the Data Access Unit action plan, national and international policy.)</p> <p>2026 – 2028</p> <p>Implement reforms through internal working groups and by integrating identified reforms into existing decision-making forums</p>	DAU (Data Access Unit) together with Deputy vice-chancellor for quality,
C. Miun advocates the recognition and inclusion of diverse research merits in the planning and assessment of research careers, such as valuing collaboration with the surrounding community in research.	<p>2025</p> <p>Initiate and implement cross-functional working groups with representatives from the Academic Appointments Councils and HR-department to identify and operationalize reforms in merits and recruitment. First steps include: mapping existing Miun and faculty policy and regulation, making gap-analyses in relation to CoARA recommendations, and identifying needs of adjustment.</p> <p>2026 – 2028</p> <p>Implement cross-functional working groups to identify and operationalize reforms in merits and recruitment. Next steps.</p>	Deans and Head of HR-department together with Deputy vice-chancellor for quality, University director
D. Miun upholds stringent standards for research quality and integrity by continually enhancing the methods of collegial research evaluation	<p>2025</p> <p>To enhance Miun's quality systems, use CoARA in the process of revising the existing quality system.</p>	Deputy vice-chancellor for quality, Deans

	<p>Initiate and implement cross-functional working groups with representatives from faculties, faculty offices and the vice chancellors office to review and adjust current research and education evaluation practices to identify and adjust gaps in relation to Miun's strategy and CoARA priorities. Engage key stakeholders.</p> <p>2026 – 2028</p> <p>Implement the reviewed and adjusted research evaluation practices done in 2025 priorities</p>	
<p>E. Miun facilitates mutual learning by exchanging practices and experiences within and beyond the Coalition through National Chapter working groups, CoARA working groups, and other networks.</p>	<p>2025</p> <p>Engage actively in national and international CoARA working groups to learn from other institutions and contribute to the broader conversation on research assessment reforms. Share best practices within the Miun community through for example workshops, reports and internal working groups.</p> <p>2026 – 2028</p> <p>Engage actively and take more responsibility in national CoARA working groups to learn from other institutions and contribute to the broader conversation on research assessment reforms. Share best practices within the Miun community through for example workshops, reports and internal working groups</p>	<p>Deputy vice-chancellor for quality, University director, Deans</p>